

Personal sampling of respirable and ultrafine particles in workplaces

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Abstract

Correlations between particle emission, respiratory exposure, and toxicity response remain much uncertain for many emerging workplaces, such as nanomaterial manufacturing and 3-D printing. Dr. Shawn Chen has been working on assessing potential worker exposure to particle emissions in different workplaces with both real-time aerosol instruments and personal samplers developed by his team. In the talk, he is showing the key concepts in the development of personal samplers and how they are applied to characterize particle emissions from different sources. The measurement results from field studies of several nanopowder manufacturing workplaces will be discussed. Besides, the method to characterize the emission from 3-D printers will be shown. The aim of this talk is to provide suggestions on how to accurately collect emitted particles from different sources to help fill the gap between respiratory exposure and health response.